

For the derivation of these equations, imagine a scenario where all virtual particles that pop into existence in one second of elapsed time in one unit of volume simultaneously pop into and out of existence at the same time for Δt seconds in 1 second intervals. In this scenario, all these virtual particles will all have the same energy and time of existence that have to do with the average values of the entire volume.

A lot of these equations may appear dimensionally inconsistent because the volume of concern is $= 1m^3$ and the time period of concern is 1 second. Those terms are left out for many of the equations.

Nomenclature:

$$\rho_{de} = \text{dark energy density} = 5.35 \times 10^{-10} \frac{\text{Joules}}{m^3}$$

$$\rho_{QM} = \text{quantum mechanics vacuum energy density} = 4.63 \times 10^{113} \frac{\text{Joules}}{m^3}$$

$$h = \text{Planck's constant} = 6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Joule} * \text{seconds}$$

$$\Delta t = \text{elapsed time}$$

$$\Delta E = \text{energy}$$

$$f = \text{frequency}$$

$$f_{total \rho} = \text{frequency due to total energy density}$$

$$c = \text{speed of light} = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$$

$$n = \text{number of virtual particles in one unit of volume}$$

$$n_{vp} = \text{total number of virtual particles popping into existence in 1 second in } 1m^3$$

$$vol = \text{arbitrary volume}$$

$$d = \text{diameter}$$

$$vp = \text{virtual particle}$$

$$G = \text{gravitational constant} = 6.6743 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg * s^2}$$

$$\gamma_{vp} = \text{wavelength of virtual particle}$$

$$velocity_{vp} = \text{velocity of virtual particle}$$

$$energy_{vp} = \text{energy of virtual particle}$$

$$d_{vp} = \text{diameter of virtual particle}$$

Derivations:

$$f = \frac{\rho_{de}}{h} = \frac{\rho_{de} \frac{\text{Joules}}{m^3}}{6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{Joules} * \text{seconds}}$$

(Planck-Einstein relation - overall frequency of virtual particles popping into existence per second in one unit of volume).

$$\Delta t = \frac{h}{4\pi\Delta E} = \frac{h}{4\pi\rho_{de}*1m^3} = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{Joule*seconds}}{4\pi\rho_{de}\text{joules}}$$

(Heisenberg uncertainty principle – gives the average lifetime of all virtual particles in one unit of volume)

$$n = f \Delta t = \frac{\rho_{de}}{h} \times \frac{h}{4\pi\rho_{de}*1m^3} = \frac{1}{4\pi} = 0.0796 \frac{\text{virtual particles}}{m^3}$$

(Number of virtual particles existing in one unit of volume overall. The reason this value is so low in one unit of volume is because virtual particles are very fleeting (small Δt) which means there are snapshots in time where there are no virtual particle present at all in one unit of volume)

$$volume_{vp_ft} = \frac{1}{n} = 4\pi = \frac{12.566m^3}{\text{virtual particle}}$$

(Volume for overall one virtual particle in existence. In this volume, there is on average one virtual particle present which is the average of all snapshots in time)

$$\text{Energy of 1 vp} = 4\pi m^3 * \rho_{de} \frac{\text{Joules}}{m^3}$$

(Energy of each virtual particle on average. Due to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle, different virtual particles will acquire different energies but for this derivation, finding the average energy of each virtual particle in one unit of volume is sufficient. The dark energy density is what is solved for, so the actual value of dark energy density is not used in the code containing all the equations of this derivation)

$$n_{vp} = f * 1 \text{ second}$$

(Number of virtual particles popping into existence in 1 second in an arbitrary volume including in the beginning scenario. For this derivation, $1m^3$ is used for the volume. The beginning scenario helps gives an understanding on why n_{vp} (number of virtual particles) = f (frequency) when deriving the equation for the diameter of a virtual particle below. In the beginning scenario, all virtual particles are simultaneously present for Δt seconds in one second intervals. The Planck-Einstein relation can be used to find the frequency associated with a certain volume. The energy, which is plugged into the Planck-Einstein relation, is calculated by multiplying the dark energy density by the volume. In one unit of volume, the total energy is equal to the dark energy density)

$$d_{vp} = \frac{d_{total \text{ in volume}}}{n_{vp}} = \frac{k * c * \Delta t}{n_{vp}} = \frac{k * c * \Delta t}{f} = \frac{k * c * h}{(4 * \pi * \rho_{de})} * \frac{h}{\rho_{de} * 1m^3 * 1s} = \frac{k * c * h^2}{(4 * \pi * \rho_{de}^2)}$$

(Diameter per virtual particle on average. Imagine lining up all the virtual particles of an arbitrary volume that pop into existence in a straight line with no space between them throughout the duration of Δt when they exist in the beginning scenario. Throughout the duration of Δt , the diameter of each virtual particles expands in this strait line in this scenario. The total velocity of expansion at the end of the line of n_{vp} virtual particles lined up with the other end fixed expands at a velocity of $k*c$. The outward velocity of the diameter of an individual virtual particle is equal to $\frac{k*c}{n_{vp}}$. The final combined diameter of these virtual particles lined up right before they annihilate in the beginning scenario is $k*c*\Delta t$. $k*c*\Delta t$ is also known as the maximum path length formula but for this derivation, it will represent the diameter of the virtual particles lined up. The diameter of each virtual particle on average becomes $\frac{k*c}{n_{vp}} * \Delta t$ right before they annihilate. Notice that this equation states that the velocity is proportional to the final diameter.

This is similar to how dark energy works on cosmic scales with the outward velocity proportional to the radius or diameter. To find the value of k, the Friedmann equation will be used later).

$$d_{vp} = \frac{k * c}{(f \cdot 4 * \pi * n_{vp})} = \frac{k * c}{(4 * \pi * f^2)}$$

(diameter per virtual particle on average (alternate equation)). In this equation, the total final diameter of n_{vp} virtual particles lined up is

$$\frac{k * c}{4 * \pi * f}. \text{ This diameter is one wavelength of } n_{vp} \text{ virtual particles}$$

combined. The reason for including the $4 * \pi$ terms is because to find the wavelength of these virtual particles combined, you must use the volume where overall one virtual particle is present on average. This volume was derived earlier. Virtual particles are assumed to have one wavelength which makes up their diameter. In the previous equation, the outward velocity of the diameter of each virtual particle is $\frac{c}{n_{vp}}$ and

that applies to this equation as well).

$$d_{vp} = \gamma_{vp} = h * \frac{\text{velocity}_{vp}}{\text{Energy}_{vp}} = h * \frac{\frac{k * c}{n_{vp}}}{\rho_{de} * 4 * \pi} = h * \frac{k * c}{\rho_{de} * 4 * \pi * f}$$

$$d_{vp} = \gamma_{vp} = \frac{k * c * h}{4 * \pi * \rho_{de} * f} = \frac{k * c * h^2}{4 * \pi * \rho_{de}^2}$$

(Diameter for a virtual particle (alternate equation 2). This derivation uses the Planck-Einstein relation initially (Energy=

$$h * \text{frequency} = \frac{h * \text{velocity}}{\gamma}) \text{ with the equation rearranged so solve for}$$

wavelength. A virtual particle has an energy of $\rho_{de} * 4 * \pi$ on average).

$$\text{volume (vp)} = \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{1}{2} * d_{vp} \right)^3$$

(Volume of each virtual particle on average).

$$\text{Energy}_{vp} = \rho_{de} * 4 * \pi$$

(Energy per virtual particle on average. Remember, the volume of one virtual particle on average is $4 * \pi$)

$$\rho_{QM} = \frac{\left(\frac{Energy}{vp}\right)}{volume (vp)} = \frac{4 * \pi * \rho_{de}}{\frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{1}{2} d_{vp}\right)^3} = \frac{4 * \pi * \rho_{de}}{\frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{1}{2} * \frac{k * c * h^2}{4 * \pi * \rho_{de}^2}\right)^3}$$

(Quantum mechanics value of the vacuum energy density which is assumed to be the energy density throughout a virtual particle. Since the quantum mechanics value of energy density applies of all volumes of space, this applies at the individual virtual particle scale. An assumption is that the current method of the cosmological constant problem assumes a 100% packed volume of virtual particles when in reality, the virtual particles are spaced which lowers the overall energy density of the vacuum of the cosmos)

$$\rho_{QM} = \frac{4 * \pi * \rho_{de}}{\left(\frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{1}{8} * \frac{k^3 * c^3 * h^6}{(64 * \pi^3 * \rho_{de}^6)}\right)\right)}$$

(Quantum mechanics value of the vacuum energy density continued)

$$\rho_{QM} = \frac{4 * \pi * \rho_{de}}{\left(\frac{\pi * k^3 * c^3 * h^6}{384 * \pi^3 * \rho_{de}^6}\right)} = \frac{1536 * \pi^3 * \rho_{de}^7}{(k^3 * c^3 * h^6)}$$

(Quantum mechanics value of the vacuum energy density continued)

$$\rho_{de} = \left(\frac{\rho_{QM} * k^3 * c^3 * h^6}{1536 * \pi^3 * time^3}\right)^{1/7} = \left(\frac{\rho_{QM} * k^3 * c^3 * h^6}{1536 * \pi^3}\right)^{1/7} = \left(\frac{\rho_{QM} * k^3 * c^3 * h^6}{1536 * \pi^3}\right)^{1/7}$$

(The equation equal to the quantum mechanics value of vacuum energy density is rearranged to make the equation equal to the dark energy density.

These equations are dimensionally inconsistent because the volume (equal to $1m^3$) and the time (equal to 1 second) cancel out and those values of volume and time are what need to be used for these

derivations. The energy density throughout virtual particle and the current value for the cosmological constant problem is assumed to be equal).

Next, the value of k will be derived.

$$H = \frac{\text{velocity}}{\text{distance}} = \sqrt{\frac{8}{3}\pi\rho_t G} = \sqrt{\frac{8}{3}\pi * 9.2 \times 10^{-10} \frac{\text{Joules}}{\text{m}^3} * 6.6743 \times 10^{-11} \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{kg} * \text{s}^2}} = 2.3 \times 10^{-18} / \text{s}$$

(Friedmann equation – used to obtain the Hubble parameter using the total energy density of the universe. This Hubble parameter will enable us to find the value of k in the earlier equations since the expansion of virtual particles behaves like dark energy on cosmological scales and is hypothesized in this report to be the explanation of what causes the expansion of the universe)

$$\text{velocity} = \sqrt{2 * \text{distance} * \text{acceleration}}$$

(Kinematic equation for velocity – without gravity affecting the acceleration due to dark energy that is proportional to radius, the equation for the Hubble parameter (H) of a virtual particle

is $\sqrt{\left(\frac{k * 0.5 * c}{4 * \pi * f_{\text{total}} \rho * \sqrt[3]{3} * 1 \text{ sec.}}\right)^2}$. Including the gravitational acceleration, the

equation is shown below:

$$\text{acceleration} = H^2 * d - \frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi \frac{(\rho_t - \rho_{de})}{c^2} * G * d^3}{d^2} = H^2 * d - \frac{4}{3}\pi \frac{(\rho_t - \rho_{de})}{c^2} * G * d$$

$$H_{\text{actual}} = \sqrt{\frac{(H^2 * d - \frac{4}{3}\pi \frac{(\rho_t - \rho_{de})}{c^2} * G * d)}{H^2 * d}} * H = \sqrt{H^2 - \frac{4}{3}\pi \frac{(\rho_t - \rho_{de})}{c^2} * G}$$

$\sqrt{\text{acceleration}}$ is proportional to velocity so that is why the square root is applied to the ratio of the acceleration with the gravitational effect to without the gravitational effect above. Next, multiply this velocity ratio by H (the Hubble parameter without gravitational effects) to get the true value of H (with gravitational effects).

$$H_{actual} = \frac{\text{velocity of } vp}{2 * \text{radius of } 4\pi \text{ volume}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{k * 0.5 * c}{4 * \pi * f_{total} \rho * \sqrt[3]{3} * 1 \text{ sec.}}\right)^2 - \frac{4}{3}\pi \frac{(\rho_t - \rho_{de})}{c^2} * G}$$

$$H_{actual} = \frac{\text{velocity of } vp}{2 * \text{radius of } 4\pi \text{ volume}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{k * 0.5 * c * h}{4 * \pi * \rho_t * \sqrt[3]{3} * 1 \text{ sec.}}\right)^2 - \frac{4}{3}\pi \frac{(\rho_t - \rho_{de})}{c^2} * G}$$

(The volume of interest in calculating the value of k is $4*\pi$ since overall one virtual particle exists in that volume. The total velocity of the radius (not the diameter) of a virtual particle in this volume is $\frac{k*.5*c}{n_{vp}} = \frac{k*.5*c}{4*\pi*f}$.

The total radius of a spherical volume of 4π is equal to $\sqrt[3]{3}$. On average, an overall one virtual particle is spaced at twice this length. The dark energy like behavior of these virtual particles is what causes the behavior of dark energy on cosmological scales. That is why the Friedmann equation was used. The value of k is iterated until this Hubble parameter value is equal to the cosmological value of the Hubble parameter. The terms on the right within the square root is the gravitational energy working against the outward velocity. The frequency depends on the total energy density this time, not just the dark energy density).

When the current quantum mechanics value of energy density is plugged into the previous equations and you solve for ρ_{de} which is the dark energy density of space, you get a value of $\rho_{de} = 5.16 \times 10^{-10} \frac{\text{Joules}}{\text{m}^3}$. The actual value is $\rho_{de} = 5.35 \times 10^{-10} \frac{\text{Joules}}{\text{m}^3}$. This is only a 3.6% error! The fact that you end up with a 3.6% error using a value that is 8.65×10^{122} orders of magnitude off from the actual value of the dark energy density increases the likelihood that these methods are correct and is a viable solution for completing the calculations for the current methods of the cosmological constant problem. Getting this small of an error using a value that is several orders of magnitude off is like hitting a small target from several miles away.

One possible explanation for the error is the quantization of space at the level of an individual virtual particle since its radius is well below the Planck length. This would increase the calculated volume of a virtual particle without changing the energy of a virtual particle since the volume contains voids. When this volume is increased, the value of vacuum energy density actually increases according to the Matlab script. The calculated vacuum energy density is just slightly below the actual value, so if this quantization of space is accounted for, that may indeed decrease the error even more.

One way to test the validity of the equations is by changing the length of a meter and adjusting the speed of light, Planck's constant, gravitational constant, and energy density of matter at the beginning of the code accordingly depending on how much you chose to change the meter. Those variables have units including the meter so dimensional analysis is required to see how much those variables scale. The equations for 'volume_1_vp_ft' and 'volume_vp' must also be changed. For example, if you double the meter, the speed of light becomes $1/2$ its value, The Planck's constant becomes $1/4$ its value, the gravitational constant becomes $1/8$ its value, the matter energy density becomes $2x$ its value, and the equations for the volumes becomes $1/8$ their values. Next, the outputted vacuum energy density does indeed double, giving additional hope that these derivations are correct.